

SECTION: FOOD SECURITY

A PUBLIC POLICY DISCUSSION OF FOOD SECURITY AND EMERGING FOOD PRODUCTION MANAGEMENT TECHNOLOGIES THAT INCLUDE DRONES, ROBOTS, AND NEW TECHNOLOGIES

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ABSTRACT: The business of food production has undergone significant revolutions through the innovations of the Industrial Revolution, a division of labor, genetically modified crops, the growth of sustainability, and use of farming robots, computers, and drones. An invasive business, economic, and public policy phenomenon that is driving technology integration in the food and agriculture industry is technological determinism. Technological determinism is the continuous integration of technologies to enhance society and existing processes and practices with little regard to institutional and organizational cultural implications. Without a doubt, technological determinism is a significant contributor for advancing the business and policy uses of technology in farming and agricultural practices. This paper uses relevant food security public policy literature to discuss the benefits and cyber risks to technology-driven food production approaches.

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1. Introduction

The world faces a litany of problems in the coming decades. A chief problem is maintaining food production to correspond to an increasing global population (Meyers & Kalaitzandoakes, 2015). One of the greatest global issues is food security. The United States Census Bureau (2015) projects that the world population will reach 9.38 billion persons by 2050, an approximate 36.5% increase over the population in 2010. The agricultural sector is listed as one of 18 critical infrastructures by the U.S. government (GAO, 2015). The business of food production has undergone significant revolutions through the innovations of the Industrial Revolution, division of labor, genetically modified crops, the growth of sustainability, and use of farming robots, computers, and drones (Anderson, 2014). An

invasive phenomenon that is driving technology integration in the food and agriculture industry is technological determinism (Nobles, 2015). Technological determinism is the continuous integration of technologies to enhance society and existing processes and practices with little regard to institutional and organizational cultural implications (Nobles, 2015). Without a doubt, technological determinism is a significant contributor to advancing the use of technology in farming and agricultural practices (Anderson, 2014). This article engages in an exploratory public policy discussion of food security and the benefits and cyber risks to technology-driven food production approaches.

Agriculture should also aim to guarantee food security for people. As stated by FAO (2008), food security is defined as a state when "all people, at all times, have physical and economic access to sufficient, safe and nutritious food for a healthy and active life." So, in order to guarantee food security to humanity, we have to be concerned with the health of earth's natural resources, soil fertility to start with (Gomiero, Pimentel, & Paoletti, 2011).

2. The research objective

The research objective of this paper is to provide a contextual review of public policy and food security literature and current events to explore technological determinism concerning farming, food production, food security, and food policy.

3. The tasks

The tasks include using a scan of current and significant literature around the use of new technologies, like drones and robots, which can assist with the efficiency of farming and food production in a manner that advances a global policy discussion around food security and food production.

4. The literature review and contexts

World population growth is the largest hurdle to sustainable agriculture and food security. Currently, about 1 billion people are chronically undernourished; this is often blamed on an inefficient trading and distribution system, additionally, it is said that there is still agricultural land to be developed leaving room to provide for the additional 2-3 billion people globally expected by 2050 (Meyers & Kalaitzandoakes, 2015). However, population expectations do not appear to be declining, or even leveling off.

Current United Nations' estimates of population stabilization at about 9 billion people by 2050 are questionable, mainly because of the young age structure of the current world population and the momentum it fosters (Meyers & Kalaitzandoakes, 2015). A variety of factors that are internal to a country affect its food security (Meyers & Kalaitzandoakes, 2015). Both net-food-importing and net-food-exporting countries could be broadly vulnerable because food security is not just about the abundance of food, nor a matter of being able to produce enough food to feed the entire population (Meyers &

Kalaitzandoakes, 2015). Problems related to lack of access to food are not merely addressed through scientific discourse on ways to boost food production...these problems are also critically tied to ownership and exchange, which are exacerbated in contexts of high levels of poverty and inequality as well as economic crises and volatility (Conceicao & Mendoza, 2009)

While population growth is the largest impediment to food production and security, there are many solutions available to help provide for humanity and protect the planet (Meyers & Kalaitzandoakes, 2015) Shifting away from traditional, commercial agricultural production toward sustainable, increasingly regional food production allows for more efficient provision of resources and increasing stewardship of the land (Meyers & Kalaitzandoakes, 2015). Adopting systems technological approaches to agricultural production and cultural unity can offer a bridge toward sustainability, and eventually the surmounting of global population increases (Meyers & Kalaitzandoakes, 2015).

4.1. Food production in the United States

One of the issues with food production in the United States comes from subsidies. We currently live in a world order guided by prices; when these principle signals for economic activity poorly reflect environmental realities (as ours currently do), the market functions incorrectly leading to massive misuse of resources (Speth, 2008). "Subsidies for agriculture can foster overloading of croplands, pollution from synthetic fertilizers and pesticides, denitrification of soils, and release of greenhouse gases..." (Speth, 2008, p. 54). It is only through internalizing all environmental costs, and redistributing subsidies fairly, that agriculture can change. "Requiring food producers to swallow the full cost of production, environmental costs included, is essential to achieving genuine reform" (McWilliams, 2009, p.33)

Another issue with current food production is the over-reliance on fossil fuel generated inputs such as chemical fertilizers and biocides. Each year, between five and six billion pounds of chemicals are added to the environment, and roughly 30 gallons of gasoline is required to produce enough fertilizer for one acre of conventionally grown corn (McWilliams, 2009). This addiction to chemical agriculture is having significant impacts on the natural environment and human health. Loss of biodiversity, soil erosion, desertification, reduction of the water table, chemical overloading, and climate change are all linked to our industrial food production (McWilliams, 2009).

A systematic approach to sustainable agriculture is illustrated by the Seven Challenges of the Asilomar Declaration for sustainable agriculture (Edwards, 2005, pp. 91-93):

- 1) Promote and sustain healthy rural communities;
- 2) Expand opportunities for new and existing farmers to prosper using sustainable systems;
- 3) Inspire the public to value safe and healthy food;
- 4) Foster an ethic of land stewardship and humaneness in the treatment of farm animals;
- 5) Expand knowledge access to information about sustainable agriculture;

6) Reform the relationship among government, industry, and agriculture; and,

7) Redefine the role of U.S. agriculture in the global community (Edwards, 2005, pp. 91-93).

Several approaches have been born of recent debate including agroecology, permaculture, aquaponics, as well as other variations of organic and local productions. Other proponents rally around the use of technologies such as genetically modified (GM) crops to provide for the hungry poor with reductions in chemical inputs. A contentious issue surrounding GM crops is the patent. GM seeds belong to the company that produced them, essentially renting them to the farmers who have to repurchase each year. According to this, the concept of "food sovereignty" has been raised by NGOs against the push forward of agribusiness actors. Sovereignty understood as the right to decide locally the use and production that does not depend on foreign actors. (Borrell, 2010)

However, should the technology move into the public sector it does have the potential to significantly reduce the dependence of chemical inputs and irrigation, while simultaneously increase crop yields (Anderson, 2014). This would allow for the production of more food on the same amount of land with fewer costs in the form of inputs (Meyers & Kalaitzandoakes, 2015). Integrating this technology is one way to alleviate some of the issues of food production.

There are two major threats to the future of food security in the United States. First is the projected population growth; the US population is planned to grow from 309 million people in 2012 to 520 people in 2050 (Pullman & Wu, 2012). Second is the finite nature and increasing costs of fossil fuels upon which conventional agricultural practices and food production are dependent (Carolan, 2013).

In the US today, there are 1.8 acres of farmable land per person available and the current amount of land needed to meet American diet assuming current standards and practices is 1.2 acres (Pullman & Wu, 2012). Assuming population increases as projected by 2050, there will be .6 acres of farmable land available per person (Pullman & Wu, 2012). This is 50% of the agricultural land required to meet the needs of the average American diet person (Pullman & Wu, 2012). This will result in one of two things: increased productivity of land/innovative solutions to land use or the need to import ½ of our food by 2050 person (Pullman & Wu, 2012). In 2011, the US imported approximately 20% of the food consumed while the American farmer exported 45 percent of their wheat, 34 percent of their soybeans, 71 percent of their almonds, and more than 60 percent of their sunflower oil (FDA Imports, 2012; USDA, 2012). If consumption and land use trends continue, it is estimated that by 2025, the United States will cease to export food (Pullman & Wu, 2012).

"Community food security exists when all community residents obtain a safe, culturally acceptable, nutritionally adequate diet through a sustainable food system that maximizes community self-reliance and social justice" (Hamm & Bellows, 2003). While the term "nutritionally adequate foods" is somewhat subjective, there should come a time in the near future when derivatives of subsidized crops as primary food ingredients are deemed "inadequate" based on long-term health effects (Pullman & Wu, 2012). The monoculture environment of agriculture supported by federal food policy is influencing the American diet and as a result, the basic food security requirement of nutrition is not being met. The

reformed policy addressing food security in the US must include must consideration of public health impacts (Carolan, 2013).

4.2. Strategies for US food security and varying viewpoints

The issue of food security in the US can be evaluated using three distinct perspectives, each requiring a different approach to reform: first, as a function of poverty and economic hardship, second as a function of dietary and behavioral habits, marketing and public policy, and third as an outcome of agricultural land use (Bellows & Hamm, 2003). The increasing population and the burden on our environment make addressing these issues sustainably more critical than ever.

4.3. Poverty

We have been trained to believe that meeting the food needs of the lowest income groups is at odds with sustainability but addressing both is perhaps the biggest opportunity the US has to benefit its citizens and the greater global community. "One potential determinant of household transitions into and out of food-insecurity status is expenditure shocks" (Fletcher, Andreyeva, & Busch, 2009). Considering food prices in the US are expected to increase three to five times by 2050, the most financially vulnerable will be increasingly at risk (Pullman & Wu, 2012). Scientific evidence supports the fact that sustainable methods like agro-ecological farming, outperform the use of chemical fertilizers in boosting food production, even in unfavorable environments; agro-ecological farming can double food production within 10 years while mitigating climate change and alleviating poverty (Ishii-Eiteman, 2011).

4.4. Diet, behavior and public policy

During the past 20 years, there has been a dramatic increase in obesity in the United States. In 2010, no state had a prevalence of obesity less than 20%; today more than one-third of adults (35.7%) are obese and approximately 17% (or 12.5 million) of children and adolescents aged 2-19 years are obese (CDC, 2012). A national epidemic and a form of food insecurity, obesity is the result of a lack of attention from both the public and private sectors on nutrition, diet, and exercise. To make matters worse, obesity is most prevalent in low-income adolescents (Beebout, 2006). The market-driven, private sector primarily promotes high-fat, high-sugar, high-salt processed foods with limited fresh fruits and vegetables in direct contrast with national dietary recommendations (Bellows & Hamm, 2003). Crop subsidies have compelled farmers to ignore other "healthier" crops such as fruits and vegetables and as a result, the market is flooded with cheap products made from the highly subsidized crops, including sweeteners in the form of high-fructose corn syrup and fats in the form of hydrogenated fats made from soybeans (Fields, 2004). Dietary reform will require education at the earliest ages, continued improvements in food labeling and possibly most important, an overhaul of the USDA Farm Bill crop subsidies that promote

the excessive use of subsidized crops as underpriced inputs in processed foods (Carolan, 2013).

Some researchers and agricultural industry professionals, believe other factors are driving obesity: less physical activity, longer work weeks and more two-worker households resulting in less time for nutritious home-cooked meals, and more children left home alone after school until parents get home from work, allowing children to be more sedentary while eating more high-caloric snacks (Field, 2004).

4.5. Agricultural land use

Modern agriculture has vast and adverse impacts on the environment: more than two-thirds of human water use is for agriculture, crop and livestock production is the main source of water pollution, and agriculture, forestry, and fishing are the leading causes of loss of the world's biodiversity (Nair, 2008). "Thus, agriculture affects the basis for its own future through land degradation, salinization, over-extraction of water, and reduction of genetic diversity" (Nair, 2008). This historical mismanagement of natural resources combined with a population that will increase by almost 70% by 2050 demands innovation and reform.

The objective of sustainable development of agriculture is "to increase food production and enhance food security in an environmentally sound way so as to contribute to sustainable natural resource management" (Rehber & Grega, 2008). Land restoration and resource conservation are being addressed through land conversion to organic farming and permaculture. While these are sustainable and efficient methods, permaculture is best suited for localized economies, and both struggle to deliver the crop yields that will be required to support a growing population (Pullman & Wu, 2012). However, when combined with other systems capable of high yields like aquaponics and agroecological farms and systems that create farmable "land" were there was none like we see with vertical and rooftop production, we begin to see the possibility of multiple disciplines working in unison to meet our current and future needs while preserving diversity in production and practice. With increased oversight and regulation, aquaculture and crops genetically modified to improve yields could also be utilized to augment the collective system.

The USDA Farm Bill currently includes support programs for sustainable development, conversion from conventional farming, and the development and use of renewable energy (to name a few) (Natural Resource Conservation Service, 2012). If "creating new programs to address high priority environmental goals" is in fact high priority as stated on the Natural Resource, more funding will need to be allocated to sustainable development and conversion of the agricultural industry (Natural Resource Conservation Service, 2012). Given the US Farm Bill has paid out more than 14 billion dollars annually to farmers of subsidized crops over the last 10 years (some years were over 20 billion) it seems a bit of budgetary reallocation could go a long way in supporting innovation and funding sustainable development (Masterson, 2011).

4.6. Sustainable recommendations for food security

Food security has been defined by the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), of the United Nations since 1971 to reflect in part our understanding of why food insecurity exists and what can be done to alleviate the condition. It was first defined from a supply side perspective, implicating shortage of food and the need for greater yields. The definition given at the 1974 World Food Summit was "availability at all times of adequate world food supplies of basic foodstuffs to sustain a steady expansion of food consumption and to offset fluctuations in production and prices" (FAO, 2003).

Gradually that definition evolved to include both a demand and supply side perspective, recognizing that access to nutritious food is an important part of the equation. In 1983, FAO defined food security as "ensuring that all people at all times have both physical and economic access to the basic food that they need" (FAO, 2008).

In 1986, the highly influential World Bank report "Poverty and Hunger" introduced the distinction between chronic food insecurity, associated with low incomes and continuing or structural poverty, and transitory food insecurity, occurring during periods of natural disasters, economic collapse or conflict. The definition of food security was thereby elaborated in terms of "access of all people at all times to enough food for an active, healthy life" (FAO, 2008). The current definition is refined in the FAO report entitled "The State of Food Insecurity 2001": Food security [is] a situation that exists when all people, at all times, have physical, social and economic access to sufficient, safe and nutritious food that meets their dietary needs and food preferences for an active and healthy life (FAO, 2008).

Looking at another definition of food insecurity, according to Shapuri, Rosen, Meade, & Gale (2009) "Food-insecure people are defined as those consuming less than the nutritional target of 2,100 calories per day per person" In these new definitions, the entitlement of individuals (and households) is emphasized. The focus is on the individual, their nutritional status, their well-being and their level of risk for undermining food security.

There are four main bureaucratic dimensions of food security: 1) physical availability of food or food supply; 2) economic and physical access, whereby an adequate supply is not enough to guarantee access to that food supply; 3) food utilization or the nutritional content of the food, and 4) stability of the three factors above over time, through political, economic or natural disaster or crisis, whereby a deficiency in any one of the three above can result in food insecurity. (FAO, 2008) This paper will discuss economic and physical access within low-income communities in the United States to nutritious foods.

The challenges to the future of food security that affect all four dimensions above, whether global, national, regional or local, revolve largely around six points: 1) population growth, 2) rising individual incomes, 3) dietary changes, 4) environmental degradation, 5) natural disasters and 6) increased use of biofuels (Pullman & Wu, 2012). These factors are not mutually exclusive; one impacts upon the other. For example, rising individual incomes lead to increased demand and pressures on supply, but it also leads to changes in diet, in particular, a greater consumption of meat and meat products. The current industrial model of animal raising is unsustainable and fosters a dependency on fossil fuels, which in turn

contributes to global warming and pressures on food supply in many parts of the world. It also contributes to environmental degradation through its reliance on chemicals (pesticides, herbicides, and fertilizers) and chemical and nutrient-laden runoff. Addressing supply and dependency on fossil fuel concerns has led to an increase in biofuels, particularly in the United States, which in turn raises food prices due to competition for grains in the marketplace. Increased food prices contribute to food insecurity among low-income populations (Pullman & Wu, 2012).

To assure food security in the face of certain population growth, our agricultural production, process, and policy need an overhaul. Beginning with the way we educate our citizens about the interrelatedness of diet and health (Carolan, 2013). The other area of focus is the use of new technologies to increase food production and lower food production costs of healthier foods.

5. Discussion of the propositions

5.1. New farming technologies that can improve food production management

Labor shortages are occurring in various parts of the world. Japan is dealing with a workforce shortage where an aging population is negatively affecting the farm labor supply. Companies are leveraging technological advances to meet the gap in the growing demand for farm laborers on corporate farms. Engineering involves technologies that extend the reach of agriculture to new means, new places and new areas of the economy. Automation will help agriculture via large-scale robotic and microrobots to check and maintain crops at the plant level (Krishna, 2016).

Air and soil sensors enable a real-time understanding of current farm, forest or body of water conditions (Krishna, 2016).

Equipment telematics allows mechanical devices such as tractors to warn mechanics that a failure is likely to occur soon (Krishna, 2016). Livestock biometrics can automatically identify and relay vital information about the livestock in real time (Krishna, 2016).

High-resolution crop sensors inform application equipment of correct amounts needed (Krishna, 2016). Optical sensors or drones are able to identify crop health across the field (Krishna, 2018).

According to Krishna (2018) Unmanned Aerial Systems (UAS) include the more narrowly defined types of unmanned aircraft (UA), Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) and remotely piloted aircraft (RPAs), and are often inaccurately referred to as "drones." However, while all these unmanned aircraft represent air vehicles that do not carry human operators onboard (but instead either fly autonomously or are remotely piloted), are expendable or recoverable, and can carry various payloads, the term UAS describes far more complex systems (Krishna, 2018). The U.S. defines unmanned aircraft (UA) as an aircraft that does not carry a human operator and is capable of flight with or without human remote control (Krishna, 2018).

In recent years, a growing number of countries have been purchasing and developing UAS not only for military purposes but also for business and farming applications (Krishna, 2018). Experts anticipate a rise in existing and potential civilian UAS uses in various industries including nonmilitary security missions (policing, firefighting, surveillance of pipeline/power lines); filmmaking; search and rescue; disaster relief; conservation of wildlife; scientific research; and multiple agricultural applications such as scouting, mapping and aerial spraying (Krishna, 2018).

Flight Computer The flight computer, also known as the aircraft control system, is used to fly the UAS, utilizing either a two-way data link (radio) for remote control or onboard computer (with GPS navigation) connected to the aircraft control system. It includes the control station(s), communication links, data terminal(s), launch and recovery systems, ground support and air traffic control interface (Krishna, 2018).

UAV Actuators are used as a mechanism to induce or control motion in mechanical systems. These devices are operated by a source of energy, typically electric current, hydraulic fluid pressure, or pneumatic pressure, to transform an input signal (usually electrical) into motion. Actuators are used in flight control, including stabilization, autopilots and vibration control (Krishna, 2018).

UAV payload is the equipment installed to perform a specific task and include for example high and low-resolution cameras or video cameras, day and night reconnaissance equipment, warfare machinery weapons, cargo and generally any equipment required for the mission the UAV is designed to perform. In agriculture, the payload serves usually for surveillance (using cameras and various optical and non-optical sensors), or delivery (e.g., pesticide, fertilizer) (Krishna, 2016; Krishna, 2018).

UAV sensors provide information needed to operate the aircraft and collect valuable information related to tasks (Krishna, 2018). A minimal autopilot system includes attitude sensors and onboard processor. Common sensors are radar and photo or video camera (Krishna, 2018).

Security issues UAV are different from conventional aircraft in the sense that a pilot onboard has "immediate control" of the aircraft. However, in the case of UAV, there is a medium the data link between the pilot at the ground control station and the aircraft. The data link is susceptible to security threats including spoofing, hijacking, and jamming. Theoretically, a hacker can create false UAV signals, jam the data link or even hi-jack the data link and take the control of UAV. Because data links are vital to the safety and seamless functioning of the UAV, this issue is important. Currently, several security features can be built into the system.

Indoor farms are using industrial robots to automate the repetitive cycles of re-planting seedlings, watering, trimming and harvesting crops, and wireless sensor networks (WSN) (Chi, Welch, Vasserman, & Kalaimannan, 2017; McCurry, 2016). These capabilities are indicative of farming and agriculture stakeholders' embracing technological determinism thinking. New innovation techniques using automation technologies are expected to boost production by over 100% per day. The use of WSN will provide farmers in disaggregated areas with agriculture expertise and support through by optimizing data usage to prevent food disruption by leveraging precision agriculture practices (Chi, Welch, Vasserman, &

Kalaimannan, 2017). By collecting and analyzing data on plant and soil performance through WSN will prevent the over usage of fertilization and irrigation, which affects the crop performance, growth and output (Chi, Welch, Vasserman, & Kalaimannan, 2017). Unfortunately, with advanced information system technologies such as WSN and hyperconnected networks and systems are prone to cyber threats such as cyber-attacks, data breach, and ransomware attacks.

Moreover, precision agriculture pertains to the use of information technologies, sensors, WSN, actuators, hyperconnected devices, and the internet of things (IoT) to combat cybersecurity threats and vulnerabilities within agriculture systems (Bertino, Choo, Georgakopolous, & Nepal, 2016; Chi, Welch, Vasserman, & Kalaimannan, 2017). Internet of things devices will continue to increase in agriculture and farming, which increases the susceptibility to cyber incidents. Another driver for the application of information communication technology (ICT) in agriculture affordability accompanied by the miniaturization of devices and mobile applications. In fact, the World Bank listed the five following factors as enablers for advancing ICT in agriculture (Szilágyi, R., 2012):

- 1) Affordability and hyperconnectivity;
- 2) Adaptability and mobile applications;
- 3) Enhanced business models and collaboration;
- 4) Data storage capabilities and exchanges;
- 5) Public sharing of agricultural data and social media.

Given that food supply is a global issue it is imperative to increase the use of ICT in less populated areas and less developed countries in search for new farmland and opportunities. The use of drones, remotely operated tractors, irrigation systems, and automated water supply are becoming common technologies in the farming and agricultural industries (Lowenberg-DeBoer, 2015). The aforementioned technologies support precision agriculture by reducing waste and predicting crop production (Lowenberg-DeBoer, 2015). The use of the internet, wireless communications, and cloud computing will continue to advance support to farmers and the global agriculture industry; however, with the expansion of ICT comes nefarious activity by malicious hackers. For example, cybersecurity and information security is an annual billion industry. Therefore, the ascendancy of ICT in farming and agriculture requires stakeholders to increase cyber awareness, cybersecurity best practices, and cyber strategy development for the agriculture industry.

The need for a cybersecurity framework is essential for farming and agriculture given that it is a critical infrastructure (Brown, Carlyle, Salmerón, & Wood, 2006). Critical infrastructure is deemed as prized U.S. capabilities that will cause a catastrophic failure to vital services if attacked or disrupted. There are 18 critical infrastructures in which 85-90 percent of these critical services are owned by private industries (Nobles, 2016). At issue is the enormous intricacy of the U.S. agriculture industry; consequently, making it difficult to protect and safeguard from malicious actors (Brown, Carlyle, Salmerón, & Wood, 2006). As agriculture and food stakeholders integrate hyperconnected and WSN capabilities to enhance food quality and production a paralleling concern is the porous nature of ICT capabilities. The U.S.

government provides a litany of resources to private and public entities cybersecurity guidance, information security, and risk management support through organizations such as the National Institute of Standards and Technology and Information Sharing and Analysis Organization. The agriculture and farming industry needs to leverage existing platforms and collaborate with academia, industry, and government to develop frameworks and guidance to protect ICT systems that are connected to commercial farms and agriculture operations.

The agriculture and farming sector will become increasingly vulnerable to the integration of ICT, cloud computing, big data analytics, WSN, and the IoT, which threats food production. Currently, the financial, healthcare and retail industries remain the top cyber targeted sectors; yet, it is only a matter of time before malicious cyber actors target agriculture and farming. According to Chi, Welch, Vasserman, and Kalaimannan (2017) the agriculture and farming cyber ecosystem require scientific foundational underpinning to support critical data and the engineering aspects of the systems. In the cyber realm, the preponderance of organizations remains reactive to cybersecurity threats and vulnerabilities; hence, stakeholders need to escalate the urgency of addressing the lack of cybersecurity protection and defenses in the agriculture because it is a critical infrastructure and so the global good supply can remain unthreatened.

Process improvements towards greater efficiency in lettuce production should reduce dependency on human labor, allowing almost 100% of water used for plant growth to be recycled, and reduce electricity consumption by a third of the current demand (McCurry, 2016). New hardier plant designs are expected to reduce dependency on pesticides while improving levels of nutrients and anti-oxidants (McCurry, 2016). By embracing new technology, current farm production facilities expect to attract and retain younger and more tech-savvy future talent (McCurry, 2016).

While solar farms do not produce food, they do produce electricity but often generate opportunity costs due to the large requirement for the limited commodity of land (Fehrenbacher, 2016). Environmental groups are increasingly pressuring large solar energy companies to re-evaluate their use of open lands by establishing areas for conservation prohibiting the proliferation of solar panel farms (Fehrenbacher, 2016). Solar energy producers are utilizing new technology in the form of aerial drones to replace the boots on the ground surveys often taking weeks and months normally completed by humans (Fehrenbacher, 2016). 3D imaging software is allowing solar farm designers to optimize the layout of solar panels to reduce the overall footprint of the solar farms (Fehrenbacher, 2016). Designing solar farms in areas as compact as possible reduces operational and construction costs while cooperating with agricultural farms in the same area (Fehrenbacher, 2016). Technological advances in the design of the solar panels and their support foundations allow movement with the sun such that fewer panels are required on the acreage, thereby increasing the output of energy per acre (Fehrenbacher, 2016). New technology utilization reduces the need to use vital agricultural lands for the production of electricity thereby enhancing agricultural land use emphasizing the need for greater environmental awareness of limited resources required for food production (Fehrenbacher, 2016).

Technology advances aiding in the flow of information is allowing decision makers access to more in-depth consumer spending information (Sturm and Yach, 2013). Government and corporate policies affecting food prices have the potential to alter consumption behavior with direct impacts to individual's overall health (Sturm and Yach, 2013). Rather than subsidizing corn and soy products, policymakers can influence healthier consumption of unprocessed foods containing fewer added sugars, fats or salts (Sturm and Yach, 2013).

Affordability correlates directly with healthy consumer choices (Park, 2016). Economics affect the ability of lower-income individuals to purchase higher cost produce. Reducing the costs of fresh produce affects the numbers of heart disease cases (Park, 2016). Estimates show as little as a ten percent lower prices in healthy food choices could prevent over half a million heart-related deaths and almost 700,000 heart attacks by the year 2030's (Park, 2016). Just adding one additional serving of fruits or vegetables could prevent over 3 million deaths from heart disease in 2 years (Park, 2016).

Policymakers armed with information based on technology and data harvesting of consumer food choices correlated with disease prevention can make better-informed decisions (Park, 2016). Funding research and subsidizing healthy foods while penalizing unhealthy food purchases has the potential to improve the overall health of a country's population (Park, 2016). Public policy affecting the health and welfare of individuals warrants further study and action necessary to alter unhealthy consumer behavior (Park, 2016). Technology advances and research have the potential to increase productivity and reduce costs of healthy produce making healthy eating a way of life (Park, 2016). Savings realized in reduced health care costs can be used to encourage increased production and consumption of garden produce (Park, 2016). Longevity and lower incidence of disease are positively correlated to lower caloric intake from fruit and vegetable consumption (Willcox, Suzuki, Donlon, Qimei, Grove, 2013).

Since the 1930's consumers in the United States have spent lower percentages of disposable income on food (Desilver, 2014). The percentage of disposable income used to buy food fell from over 30 percent to less than 10 percent in the last 90 years (Desilver, 2014). However, caloric intake rose over 20 percent in the same timeframe. Researchers argue having greater access to cheaper but healthier produce does not necessarily correlate to a thinner population (Desilver, 2014). While few disagree with the benefits of healthy dietary choices by eating more fruits and vegetables, increased caloric intake often results in weight gain despite the additional consumption of produce (Desilver, 2014).

Another possible explanation of the increase in obesity rates is correlated with iron deficiencies (Zhao, Zhang, Shen, Fang, Wang, & Wang, 2015). Comparative studies in the US show a strong correlation between overweight/obese individuals and non-overweight participants (Zhao et al., 2015). Using technology to improve the nutrient value of foods, including iron, has the potential to affect obesity rates, and associated diseases (Zhao et al., 2015). Researchers studied 13,393 overweight/obese individuals and 26,621 non-overweight participants. Findings demonstrated a significant risk of iron deficiencies in overweight/obese individuals (Zhao et al., 2015). Symptoms of anemia include low energy and fatigue which are often remedied through self-medication with increased caloric intake of high sugar and caffeine-containing foods (Zhao et al., 2015). Researchers are also

beginning to recognize the link between obesity and iron deficiencies found in early childhood (del Giudice, Santoro, Amato, Brienza, Calabrò et al., 2009; Sonnweber, Röss, Nairz, Theurl, Schroll, Murphy et al., 2012).

Food insecurity is defined as a condition of very low food security associated with decreased nutrient intake and overall poor health of individuals, especially children (Zhao et al., 2015). Iron deficiency anemia has been linked to children in food insecure household (Zhao et al., 2015). Children between ages of 12 and 15 in food-insecure households were 2.95 times more likely to be iron deficient showcasing the need for successful intervention programs to improve food security among children (Zhao et al., 2015). The need for better technology to monitor and improve farming techniques with nutrient-dense foods is paramount to increase dietary consumption of iron-rich foods (Eicher-Miller, Mason, Weaver, McCabe, & Boushey, 2009). Technology advances must include the better production of nutrient-rich foods, greater access to those foods, and proper monitoring of the nutrient concentration in the agricultural products from the soil and subsequent absorption of vital nutrients from those foods (Zhao et al., 2015).

New technologies like drones are giving farmers and scientists alike greater access to real-time monitoring and data on crop performance from both a production standpoint and a nutrition standpoint (Anderson, 2014). Applying the correct amount of fertilizers, and plant nutrients for a proper soil base are required to maximize farm yields (Anderson, 2014). Soil samples can be analyzed using GPS coordinates combined with drone technology to better analyze the soil base for optimal plant seeding, growth cycles, and harvesting techniques (Chuchra, 2016). Nutrient monitoring for both plants and consumption based on available rainfall or irrigation practices can better allow farmers and researchers to know what plants need in certain soil types and how to implement better weed control (Anderson, 2014).

6. Final summation

With global populations are expected to reach 9 billion by 2050, the need for greater agricultural capacity is ever increasing (Chuchra, 2016). Drone technologies leverage machines and information allowing for improvements in farming practices and processes (Chuchra, 2016). The US Department of Agriculture's (USDA) National Institute of Food and Agriculture (NIFA) provided over \$2 Million in grants for technology-based improvements in agriculture. Smart mobile machines are capable of monitoring individual crop health in terms of nutrient, insecticide, pesticide, and water requirement (Anderson, 2014). Aerial agricultural drones offer farmers advanced sensing and imaging capabilities for increasing yields and reducing crop damage (Anderson, 2014). Smart mobile machines can enable farmers and researchers to monitor crop disease, parasites, and perform a host of mechanical actions such as weeding, planting, pruning, and harvesting (Chuchra, 2016).

The rate of technology development and the degree of innovation in future technologies will greatly influence the stability, and certainly the productivity, of farming and food production (Chuchra, 2016). Before 2000 these innovations were focused on areas like genetically modified crops, advances in the use of nutrients, and new pest control products (Chuchra, 2016). Today these advances include the use of farming drones, farming robots,

solar technologies, water collection and use technologies, computational technologies, remote sensing advancements, geographical location devices, and even data analytics to improve the effectiveness and efficiency of farming and food production (Chuchra, 2016).

According to Chuchra, (2016) the major advantage of these new technologies is the ability to use technology to check and sense health of each crop in real time and respond as needed with the required nutrients, insecticide, pesticide, water, and big data analytics. Farming robotic technology allows additional manpower without the human limitations to tend to crops, collect soil samples, apply water, spray pesticides, perform mechanical weeding, mowing, harvesting crops, and even accumulate data with the use of sensors and cameras (Chuchra, 2016). Agricultural drones or unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) have the ability to use sensors to track weather changes, data imagery, and data analysis to improve efficiency and farming results (Chuchra, 2016). These new technologies and robotic advances have great potential increase crop yields; proactively address issues with soil erosion; and improve farming environmental impacts through the reversal of the loss of soil carbon (Chuchra, 2016). However, it is vital to protect these technological capabilities from malicious actors to ensure the agricultural sector remains capable of producing an ample food supply.

These new technologies are creating the need for new educational and new awareness programs to inform and train farmers on the existence and utilities of these new advances and processes to include cybersecurity awareness programs. This awareness should include university and high school programs where students studying agriculture work students in robotics, computer science, cyber security, information security, and engineering are required to engage learning team projects that require them to work with farmers and food producers on actual farms. This would ensure that these technologies are being utilized correctly. These technologies should also be included in funding related to humanitarian aid and hunger aid in developing and underserved countries as a means of advancing the food security of those worldwide.

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